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ABSTRACT:

The article deals with various approaches to assessing speech, communicative qualities of speech. It also emphasizes main communicative qualities of speech as relevance, richness, purity, accuracy, consistency, accessibility, expressiveness and correctness.

Keywords: speech etiquette, social relations, the communicative qualities of speech, specific situations

INTRODUCTION:

Nowadays the conditions of foreign language communication in the modern world, when a foreign language is a means of communication, cognition, obtaining and accumulating information, predetermined the need for mastering all types of speech activity: speech etiquette and listening comprehension of speech in a given foreign language, as well as the rules of speech etiquette, reading and writing.

Speech etiquette is an important element of the culture of the people, a product of human cultural activity and an instrument of such activity. Speech etiquette is an integral part of the culture of human behavior and communication. In the expressions of speech etiquette, the social relations of a particular era are recorded. Being an element of national culture, speech etiquette is distinguished by a vivid national specificity. The specificity of greetings and all kinds of information when meeting with different nations is very interesting.

Among the various approaches to assessing speech (and its effectiveness in particular), the most productive approach is from the standpoint of analyzing the degree of speech compliance with the conditions of communication and the communicative tasks of speech partners, that is, from the standpoint of communicative expediency. It is this approach that can be carried out when assessing speech from the standpoint of the communicative qualities of speech (BN Golovin's term, introduced by him in 1976 in his work "Foundations of the culture of speech") [1,126]. According to the definition of the scientist, "the communicative qualities of speech are the real properties of its content or formal side. It is the system of these properties that determines the degree of communicative perfection of speech." B.N. Golovin reviewed each of the previously known advantages of speech in a new way

and systematized them, tracing the dependence of speech on non-speech structures in each of the aspects. The communicative situation and its components were thus closely related to the communicative qualities of speech. The communicative qualities of speech cover all aspects of the text, and their ratio and the degree of manifestation in the text depend on the genre and style of the statement, on the individual characteristics of the communicants. The main communicative qualities of speech are relevance, richness, purity, accuracy, consistency, accessibility, expressiveness and correctness. Each of these qualities is manifested in speech to varying degrees and in different ratios with other properties of speech. Thus, the purpose of this work is to explain what speech is; consider the basic communicative qualities of speech. The word "speech" denotes a specific human activity, therefore, to characterize both its sides, this word in linguistics is used in two main meanings: the process of speaking (orally) or writing (in writing) itself is called speech, and those speech works (utterances, oral and written texts), which represent a sound or graphic product (result) of this activity. Language and speech are closely interconnected, since speech is language in action, and that in order to achieve a high culture of speech, language and speech must be distinguished.

How is speech different from language?

First of all, the fact that language is a system of signs, and speech is an activity that proceeds as a process and is presented as a product of this activity. And although speech is built in one language or another, this is the most important difference, which, for various reasons, determines others.

Speech is a way of implementing all the functions of the language, primarily communicative. Speech arises as a necessary response to certain events of reality (including speech), therefore, unlike language, it is deliberate and focused on a specific goal.

Speech is primarily material - it sounds orally, and in writing it is recorded with the help of appropriate graphic means (sometimes different from the given language, for example, in another graphic system (Latin, Cyrillic, hieroglyphic writing) or with the help of icons, formulas, drawings etc.). Speech depends on specific situations, unfolds in time and is realized in space. Speech is created by a specific person in specific conditions, for a specific person (audience), therefore, it is always specific and unique, because even if it is reproduced with the help of certain recordings, circumstances change and it turns out the same thing that is usually said about: "You cannot enter the same river twice." At the same time, theoretically, speech can last indefinitely (with and without interruptions). In fact, our whole life from the time we begin to speak, and until we say the last word, is one big speech in which circumstances, addressee, subject of speech, form (oral or written) change, etc., but we keep talking (or writing). And with our last word, speech (only already written or not our oral) will continue. In this regard, speech develops linearly, i.e. we say one sentence after another in a specific sequence. The process of oral speech is

characterized by those that speech proceeds at a certain (sometimes changing) tempo, with a greater or lesser duration, the degree of loudness, articulatory clarity, etc.

Expressive speech is speech that can maintain attention, arouse the listener's (or reader's) interest in what is said (written). The main condition for expressiveness is that the author of the speech has his feelings, thoughts, his position, his own style. Expressiveness usually means originality, originality, surprise. In this regard, expressive speech is always new, "fresh" and creative. It is in this way that she is able to arouse the interest and approval of those to whom she is intended.

What does the expressiveness of speech depend on?

There is no need to talk about any great influence of speech, if the speaker speaks indistinctly, in a husky, barely audible voice, does not clearly pronounce the words, i.e. does not know the elementary technique of speech. Proficiency in speech technique is the foundation of speech culture.

The components of speech technique are diction, breathing, voice.

Each word, and in a word, each sound must be pronounced clearly - this is the main requirement of diction.

The outstanding theater figure K.S. Stanislavsky spoke very figuratively about the impression that bad diction makes on the audience: "A word with substituted letters seems to me ... a man with an ear for a mouth, with an eye for an ear, with a finger for a nose. A word with a crumpled beginning is like a person with a flattened head. A word with an unspecified end reminds me of a man with amputated legs ... When the words merge into one shapeless mass, I remember flies caught in honey." [2,145]

Fuzzy, sloppy, illiterate speech is unpleasant in everyday life. It offends our hearing, our aesthetic sense. But it is already completely unacceptable for a lecturer.

Deficiencies in diction (unless they are associated with some shortcomings of the vocal apparatus) are the result of a bad habit, deeply rooted in childhood, of saying "lazily," casually, sluggishly pronouncing words. Therefore, in order to eliminate these shortcomings, you need to control how you speak, lecturing, speaking at a meeting, in everyday life (whether you crumple words, "swallow" endings, if you sip words through your teeth, etc.) [3.17].

For the orator, the voice, its timbre, shades are important. The strength of the voice is not decisive, but it should be borne in mind that the audience (listeners) gets tired, lulls both a very quiet and a loud voice. The tone of speech is important. The speech should not be arrogant, instructive.

The semantic perception of speech largely depends on the rate of speech. Defining perception as a counter process of thinking, we must take into account two points: the listener needs to have time to comprehend the incoming information and remember the main provisions of what they are talking about [4,12].

According to experimental data, the optimal condition for easily perceived speech is the average rate of pronunciation. The presentation of complex material

dictates a slower pace of speech, while turning to facts, phenomena associated with sensory experience, life associations requires a relatively accelerated pace. Too slow speech rate is poorly perceived. The text does not sound in phrases, but in separate words[6,282].

One should be especially attentive to the expressive role of intonation (pitch, strength, timbre, rate of speech, pauses). There is a hypothesis that intonation preceded language. According to experimental data, a child masters intonation models (for example, expression of pleasure, anger) at the age of six months to a year, and much later learns the vocabulary and grammar of his native language. In communication, intonation serves as a concretizer of the meaning of an utterance in a certain situation. Thanks to it, one can understand, for example, that the good words spoken to somebody actually contain a threat, and a neutral official phrase – disposition[5,68]

Intonation allows people to emphasize the logical and emotional significance of the statement. The brighter the emotional responsiveness of a person, the richer his speech is in melodic expressiveness. Speech, devoid of proper melodic accents, is insensitive. Here speaker cannot give ready-made recipes related to the use of intonation in everyday life. There is only one rule to remember: intonation is a mirror of one's emotional life; the culture of feelings and emotional relationships is inextricably linked with the culture of intonation design of the statement[7,104].

For intonation, it is important to observe pauses. Smooth speech sometimes gives the impression of memorization, so the listeners may not like it, and some speakers use recall pauses to create the impression of impromptu speech. Logical pauses, as mentioned above, help to clarify the meaning of the statement[8,138].

In order for speech to be expressive, proverbs, sayings, aphorisms are used, as well as tropes: metaphors, comparisons of hyperbole, epithets. However, it should be remembered that these pictorial tools should not be overused.

Written speech can also be fast or slow, clear (legible) or indistinct (illegible), more or less voluminous, etc. That is, the materiality of speech can be illustrated by various examples. Language, in contrast to speech, is believed to be ideal, i.e. it exists outside speech as a whole only in the minds of those who speak this language or study this language, and also as a part of this whole - in various dictionaries or reference books.

Speech is, as a rule, the activity of one person - a speaker or a writer, therefore it is a reflection of the various characteristics of this person. Consequently, speech is initially subjective, because the speaker or writer himself selects the content of his speech, reflects his individual consciousness and individual experience in it, while language, in the system of meanings expressed by it, captures the experience of the collective, the "picture of the world" of the people speaking it.

In addition, speech is always individual, since people never use all the means of language and are content with only part of the language means in accordance with

their level of knowledge of the language and the conditions of a particular situation, choosing the most suitable ones. As a result, the meanings of words in speech may differ from those that are strictly defined and fixed by dictionaries. In speech, situations are possible in which words and even individual sentences receive a completely different meaning than in language, for example, with the help of intonation. Speech can also be characterized by indicating the psychological state of the speaker, his communicative task, attitude towards the interlocutor, sincerity.

Speech is not limited to only linguistic means. The composition of speech means also includes those that belong to non-linguistic (non-verbal, or non-verbal): voice, intonation, gestures, facial expressions, posture, position in space, etc.

All these differences between speech and language relate primarily to speech as a process of using language, therefore, although with a stretch, they are grounds for opposing them, since in this regard, the creation of speech as a process proceeds in many stages and partially coincides with the boundaries of the largest unit of language: with sentence boundaries. If we talk about speech as a result of this process, i.e. as a text. That description of speech at this level, in principle, cannot have common criteria with the language, since they are completely inapplicable to the language.

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